

SCIENTIFIC AND THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE FORMATION OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCIES IN STUDENTS WITH HEARING IMPAIRMENTS IN PRIMARY SCHOOL READING LESSONS

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Abstract: This article discusses the scientific and theoretical foundations of the formation of communicative competencies in students with hearing impairments in primary school reading lessons. An analysis of the positive effect of the use of pedagogical technologies in the development of oral speech in reading lessons in a special school was carried out.

Keywords: reading lessons, scientific and theoretical foundations, students with hearing impairments, communicative competence, reading, literary and creative activity, technology, methods

Introduction.

The ability of a child with hearing impairment to become a fully formed person in accordance with the requirements of the time, to actively participate in society, and to effectively socialize depends on the correct formation of communicative competence, since speech is a means of communication, a national treasure, and a powerful tool for education, enlightenment, and creativity. Therefore, it is important to teach every person to master speech and fully express their thoughts. In the field of national surdopedagogy, the scientific research of D.Sh.Azimova, F.Alimkhodjayeva, N.Bekmurodov, Z.N.Mamarajabova, D.Nazarova, Kh.Rakhimova, R.Rustamova, K.G.Sadirova, G.Temurova, U.Fayziyeva, F.U.Qodirova, M.M.Qodirov, D.B.Yakubzhanova emphasizes that hearing impairment in most cases leads to speechlessness, severe speech disorders or general speech underdevelopment due to this defect. These scientific views make it possible to determine the characteristics of the speech mechanism of deaf and hard-of-hearing children, the specificity of their hearing impairment. R. Rustamova noted, "The earlier a defect in a deaf child is detected, the more accurately diagnosed and the work is organized, the greater the chance of eliminating the defect in the child. Otherwise, the child will lag behind in mental development, that is, he will develop limited by the social environment. No matter how strong the attention of parents and loved ones is, if a special approach is not organized, the general development of the child will lag behind. Hearing impairment negatively affects the development of a child's speech. Therefore, any impairment in hearing perception is a major obstacle to the

development of speech. The vocabulary decreases, the grammatical structure of speech, and the pronunciation of sounds are disrupted. In addition, a child with hearing impairment is deprived of the opportunity to perceive speech addressed to him.

As the impairment of hearing perception deepens, the speech impairment deepens. If children with hearing loss or hearing loss do not receive special training, they may become completely speechless (mute) "The inability of a person to master speech due to impaired auditory perception, and therefore his isolation from members of society, creates a number of problems in finding his place in social life. These are due to various interdependent reasons, in this regard, L.S. Vygotsky says: "Social education leads to the underdevelopment of speech, the underdevelopment of speech leads to isolation from the community, and isolation from the community, in turn, stops social education and the development of speech."

Within the framework of the study, the information on the disclosure of the "path from thought to speech" based on the analysis of the literature leads to a number of conclusions in the practice of teaching language to deaf and hard of hearing children: the communicative competence of a child with hearing impairment is the generation of language phenomena, which develops as a result of the perception of adult speech and the activity of one's own speech; the communicative competence of a child with hearing impairment constitutes the core of various areas of mental development of language and speech (thinking, memory, emotions, imagination); the formation of the communicative competence of a child with hearing impairment is the leading direction of teaching the mother tongue, the issue of forming language generalizations, the simplest understanding of language and speech phenomena; the conditions for the development of the communicative competence of a child with hearing impairment, their own speech are provided through a specially organized system aimed at understanding language phenomena. Based on the existing classifications proposed by D.Azimova, Z.N.Mamarajabova, T. Yu. Kuligina, D. Yu.Alekseyevsky, O.L. Belyaeva, A.B. Goroshkov, a classification of communicative speech skills was developed: "Communicative competence is the ability to determine the sequence and logic of presenting the main and auxiliary information, the selected material, its compositional structure, and the selection and use of linguistic means for the description of the content of the text in reading lessons."

The target, informative-substantive, content-compositional, communicative components of students with hearing impairments were described as components of the communicative competence. The target component of communicative competence is the ability to communicate in a communicative situation, taking into account the communicative task, the communication environment, state and interpret the author's communicative goal; the ability to switch communicative intentions; It includes the ability to express a communicative goal using verbal and non-verbal means, intonation, facial expressions, and gestures. The informative-content component of communicative competence represents the oral presentation of the content of the text being studied in a reading lesson. The group of skills of the informative-content component of communicative competence includes the ability to select words and information necessary to implement a communicative goal; the ability to identify and clarify the theme and main idea of the text, select speech material in accordance with the theme and main idea of the text, and reveal micro-themes of the text. In reading lessons, it is considered a content-compositional component that ensures the correct structure of the text. This component includes the ability to distinguish parts of the text; The ability to reconstruct parts of the introductory and concluding text; summarizes the ability to plan and present the content coherently and concisely. The communicative component of communicative competence requires not only finding specific means of expressing one's thoughts in reading lessons, ensuring the correctness, clarity, richness and stylistic accuracy of speech, but also fully and adequately expressing the communicative goal.

Pedagogical opportunities for the formation of communicative competencies in students with hearing impairments in primary school reading lessons: organizing pedagogical activities based on the practical application of methods for enriching students' vocabulary, defining word meanings, creating conditions for speech communication, expanding their speech practice, understanding and differentiating words, phrases, and text in the literary work being studied, and developing interest in reading literary works in students with hearing impairments, knowledge of the components of the book, and the complementarity and consistency of the activities of perceiving the content of the work and describing its content; as components of communicative competence, as a purposeful, informative-substantive, content-compositional, communicative formation forms, the system of integration of reading lessons in the classroom and out of class with speech development, visual activities,

technology, development of auditory perception and pronunciation skills formation exercises was envisaged.

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